

ERATOSTHENES

Secure management of IoT devices lifecycle through identities, trust and distributed ledgers

D2.4 Automatic deployment language and tools for trust agents

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Glossary of used terms and abbreviations

Table 1. Terms and abbreviations.

Abbreviation / Term	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DoW	Description of Work
DT	Digital Twin
DTA	Deployer of Trust Agents (or Trust Agent Deployer)
DTDLE	Digital Twin Definition Language
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IoT	Internet of Things
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
OS	Operating System
PoC	Proof of Concept
RPM	Remote Patient Monitoring
RQL	Resource Query Language
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
TA	Trust Agent
TMB	Trust Manager and Broker
WoT	Web of Things

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the development state of the Deployer of Trust Agents (DTA) component. This work extends upon the results previously presented in Deliverable D2.2 'Prototype of Threat Modelling and Deployer of Trust Agents', which mainly focused on the high-level design and architecture of the DTA. The main goal of this report is to provide the reader with an understanding of what DTA component is, its role in the overall ERATOSTHENES architecture, as well as some hands-on information on deploying and running the developed service. More specifically (and in line with the earlier deliverable), this report contains:

- A technical and implementation-centric discussion is provided of the DTA component with specific attention on the key elements and design decisions, as well as the possibilities for integration with the overall ERATOSTHENES architecture, and its practical usage in the context of the project pilot.
- With a reference to a project pilot, the developed implementation is described with an emphasis on how to execute and adopt the tool.
- The report also contains a summary of the scientific novelty underpinning the developed functionality, comparing it to the state of art and practice.
- Outline for further work, experimentation and trainings are discussed, focusing on improving the scalability and usability of the tool, as well as its future integration with the TA recovery mechanism (in the context of Task 2.5 'Automated recovery process of trust agents').

2 Introduction

2.1 Mapping ERATOSTHENES outputs

Purpose of this section is to map ERATOSTHENES Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 2: Adherence to ERATOSTHENES GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

ERATOSTHENES GA Component Title	ERATOSTHENES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.4: Automatic deployment language and tools for trust agents	This deliverable includes the T2.3 outputs, the source code for the deployment language, local deployment engine, global fleet assignment engine, auxiliary services for building, updating and trustworthiness assurance of the deployed TAs.	Section 4 contains the main research and technical contributions of T2.3 achieved for this deliverable so far. Section 5 highlights the scientific novelty of the work with respect to the state of the art.	T2.3 aims to enable the deployment of device-specific TAs to a distributed fleet of managed connected devices in the ERATOSTHENES ecosystem. This deliverable reports on the main technical (i.e., design + implementation) details, as well as the scientific underpinnings of this work.
TASKS			
Task 2.3 Automated Deployment of Trust Agents [Chapter 3, section 3.1.3, Description of the Work packages (WP2)]	The main research activities in this task are three-fold: (i) a deployment modelling language for the trust management mechanisms, which will be used by application developers to specify the trust agents they want to deploy on their devices, the configuration of the agents and the connection with the other application components;	Sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.4	The deployment language is built on top of the existing digital twin meta-model used by Eclipse Ditto. We have extended the default meta-model to accommodate the concepts related to the multi-dimensional context of managed devices. These continuously monitored contextual properties in turn will drive the targeted TA assignment and deployment.
	(ii) the local deployment engine that actually deploys the agents to the target devices according to the deployment model;	Sections 4.2.3, 4.2.4, and 4.2.5.	Using the 'Desired-Reported Property' pattern the deployment engine is able to monitor the status of each TA deployment and push the required updates selectively to target devices, if needed. For the actual deployment, the DTA component relies on several device-specific and platform-specific adapter implementations.

	and (iii) the global fleet assignment mechanism that automatically computes which variants of the agents should be deployed to which devices, within a fleet of large numbers of heterogeneous IoT devices.	Sections 4.2.3, 4.2.4, and 4.2.5.	<p>In simpler cases, when there is only one contextual property to consider (e.g., CPU architecture), the assignment is implemented at the code level.</p> <p>In more complex cases, the DTA component takes into consideration the multi-dimensional context collected from target devices to assign matching TAs. Using Eclipse Ditto's built-in query language (RQL) it is possible to define complex multi-parameter and/or nested queries, which will fetch only a subset of targeted devices matching the contextual requirements.</p>
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The deliverable starts with an executive summary (Section 1). Section 2 then introduces the overall deliverable, explains the position of its content in the broader context of the Description of Work (DoW), maps the discussed prototype and technology to the ERATOSTHENES outputs, and discusses how the reviewer comments were addressed. Section 3 **Error! Reference source not found.** then provides an in-depth positioning of the work in the context of the overarching architecture as developed in WP1. Section 4 is dedicated to the actual description of the developed DTA component, whereas Section 5 highlights the scientific novelty underpinning the described work. Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2.3 Adherence to 1st EC Review Comments and Recommendations

This section summarises responses and document updates following the EC review that took place on 8 February 2023. All reviewers' comments were effectively taken under consideration and details for each (and the related document updates) have been included in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Addressing the reviewers' comments.

Review Comment(s) (as provided by the reviewers)	Adherence and Document Update (Short reply and reference to the chapter that details the reply)
Clarify the innovation aspect in comparison with the current state of the art. Often it is not clear what is the innovative aspect of a product, or how it progresses beyond state of the art.	Section 5 (Research and Scientific Innovation) maps the current state of the art in the domain of Software assignment and Deployment at scale. It also describes the novelty of the work reported in this deliverable and how it advances the state of the art.
Recommendation to make the linked source code available for public deliverables or explain that it is not available.	The source code associated with this deliverable has been made available via the ERATOSTHENES project code repository (cf. Section 3.4).
Question regarding the scalability of the individual components with respect to the number of managed devices in the fleet.	As explained in Section 3.3 and throughout Section 4, the design and implementation of the DTA component are driven by the principles of modularity, extensibility, and decoupled asynchronous communication. Also, the DTA component is built on top of existing reliable tools, whenever possible, such as Eclipse Ditto

	as an underlying digital twin platform, which has been tested in large-scale enterprise scenarios. All these ensure that the DTA functionality will address the scalability challenge whenever needed.
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3 Architecture Orientation and Industrial Requirements

This section discusses the role of the DTA component in the context of the broader ERATOSTHENES architecture.

3.1 Architectural Positioning and design decisions

Figure 1. Graphical overview of the overall ERATOSTHENES architecture (adopted from Deliverable D1.3). DTA is part of the Trust Manager & Broker, depicted at the centre of the figure.

This deliverable provides the description of a key component in the edge layer of the ERATOSTHENES technology stack, of which the overall architecture is depicted in Figure 1.

Being part of a larger Trust Manager & Broker (TMB) module, the DTA is responsible for managing the lifecycle of the TAs deployed on edge devices within the ERATOSTHENES framework. This means that the DTA component not only handles the initial deployment of TAs (which remains the most important step), but also manages the consequent steps, including updates, rollbacks, and recovery (where it is an integral step in the TA recovery process developed in the context of Task 2.5). To this end, the DTA can collect various contextual information from managed devices at run-time, as well as propagate down software management commands (deploy, update, roll-back, recovery). At the same time, the DTA also keeps track of available TAs to match and assign them to target devices based on their multi-dimensional context.

DTA component is also an integral part of the TA recovery mechanism (Task 2.5 'Automated recovery process of trust agents'), where it is used as one of the common options either for reverting a malfunctioning/compromised TA to its original trusted state, or completely replacing it with a different upgraded/patched version.

3.2 Business, Industrial Positioning and End-User Requirements

The DTA module is responsible for delivering TAs to target devices within the ERATOSTHENES ecosystem. As such, this tool implements the scalable deployment of TAs across a wide and heterogeneous fleet of managed devices, and as such contributes to addressing the requirements listed in Table 4 (adopting the numbering scheme from Deliverable D1.2). These requirements primarily concern the project's Pilots 1 (Connected Vehicles) and 2 (Smart Health) and have been identified and validated through interaction with the pilot providers during the project implementation, and – more specifically – in the context of Task 5.6 'Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings'.

Table 4: Mapping between Pilot case requirements and the DTA component.

Req ID	Description	How addressed
P1_FR_09	Automatic and trustworthy deployment of software updates	The DTA component already supports Docker-ised software deployment and can be further extended to support more generic software deployment and management functionality through specific adapters.
P1_FR_21	Context driven automatic deployment of trust management agents	Trust agents are assigned and deployed in a tailored, context-aware manner. Contextual properties are continuously collected at run-time for the deployment engine to assign the correct TAs.
P2_FR_08	Manage device lifecycle (certification, deployment, upgrade, decommissioning, recovery)	The TA deployment is part of the initial device enrolment, as well as possible recovery actions requiring the original TA to be replaced.
P2_FR_09	Automatic deployment and update of software	The DTA component already supports Docker-ised software deployment and can be further extended to support more generic software deployment and management functionality through specific adapters.
P2_NFR_03	Increase the average speed of software updates	The DTA is implemented in an asynchronous and scalable manner via the MQTT channel and the 'Desired-Reported Property' pattern, meaning that as soon the device appears online it will receive the required software updates within a pre-defined polling interval (1 min), provided a stable network connection.

3.3 Methodology

As this development iteration has focused on adoptability and integrability, we have taken an approach of architectural design to improve the aspects of coupling to application-specific details, and separation of concerns. In addition, we have improved documentation of code and included a tutorial. Also, given the cyber-physical nature of managed devices within the distributed fleet, there are three main design decisions that underpin the design and implementation of the TA Deployer:

- **Decoupled architecture:** managed devices may unexpectedly crash, unpredictable lose network connection and then appear back online. To accommodate such ad-hoc behaviour and prevent bottlenecks, the communication between involved software components is implemented using the pub-sub messaging based on MQTT.
- **Asynchronous communication:** for the same reason, it is important that any TA updates initiated by the DTA are guaranteed to be delivered to target devices no matter how long they stay offline. This also means that the status of each device is continuously monitored and stored to apply the required changes when it gets back online. This can be implemented using the prominent DT pattern, which enables real-time monitoring of devices and comparing of the reported properties against the desired ones.
- **Hierarchical architecture and extensibility:** to prevent single points of failure and distribute the workload within the managed fleet of heterogenous devices, functionally similar devices that require the same TA are grouped together. This introduces an extra layer of filtering and load-balancing functionality in between the centralised DTA and numerous devices within the managed fleet. Thanks to this hierarchical architecture, where generic functionality is separated from device-specific implementations, the DTA will be able to accommodate new types of devices and TAs in the future.

Additionally to these main requirements, the design and implementation of the DTA component is driven by several non-functional requirements, such as the availability of a GUI, user-friendliness, intention to re-use existing software libraries, etc.

3.4 Code Availability

- The lower-level functionality of the DTA component (i.e., sub-fleet manager, device adapters, MQTT-based clients for both upstream and downstream communication with the DT platform) is hosted at <https://ci-cysec.eng.it/gitlab/ERATOSTHENES/trudeplo>. The repository includes a README file with general instructions.
- The higher-level functionality of the DTA component, including the GUI and the back end of the DT platform, has been implemented on top of open-source Eclipse Ditto framework. The project repository is <https://ci-cysec.eng.it/gitlab/ERATOSTHENES/dta>. The repository includes a README file with general instructions.

4 Automatic Deployment of Trust Agents

The DTA component has been designed and implemented in a modular, loosely coupled manner with MQTT being the main transportation/communication layer between these components. More specifically, the umbrella term ‘DTA’ refers to a collection of software components distributed across the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, all united by the shared functionality of deploying and managing TAs. This section will guide the reader through the main elements of this component-based design, starting from the overall conceptual architecture.

4.1 Conceptual Architecture

Figure 2. Conceptual architecture of the DTA component.

This section discusses the design and functionality of the DTA component. Figure 2 above illustrates its main elements, which is spread across the following three logical layers:

- **The IoT/Edge devices**, constituting the managed fleet, which will be assigned and deployed with TAs suited to their specific context and requirements (i.e., hardware, software, user, business logic).
- A **trusted domain** is a logical network that contains a group of co-located devices and several ERATOSTHENES services. At least one device has sufficient resources to run the basic fleet management functionality (or part of it, such as remote device deployments).
- The **public cloud** includes everything outside of the domains, which does not have the strict control by the fleet managers.

The front end of the DTA component is the fleet management tool implemented on top of Eclipse Ditto¹ DT platform. Ditto acts as IoT middleware, providing an abstraction layer for IoT solutions interacting with physical devices via the DT pattern. Managed devices are integrated via a device connectivity layer – i.e., an MQTT broker like Eclipse Mosquitto² in our case. DTs managed in Ditto can also be integrated into other backend systems by using several supported protocols. This functionality allowed us to build bi-directional communication between the Ditto back-end and the implemented adapters via MQTT, as well as to develop a user-friendly administration GUI for live status updates and interaction with the devices. At the back end, the DTA component relies on so-called sub-fleet controllers and device-specific adapters for TA deployment. The main deployment tools and patterns underpinning the DTA components are explained in the next subsection.

¹ <https://eclipse.dev/ditto/>

² <https://mosquitto.org/>

4.2 Main Deployment Tools

4.2.1 Eclipse Ditto: a DT platform for building the DTA functionality

As the technological baseline on top of which we have developed the DTA component, we have used Eclipse Ditto³ - an open-source framework for building DTs of Internet-connected devices with extensible modelling and built-in querying languages.

As already explained, by using a device management platform, edge application providers can remotely provision, monitor, and maintain their device, as well as push software updates whenever a new version is released. In recent years, all these tasks have been underpinned by the prominent concept of DTs. Simply put, DTs are virtual models designed to accurately reflect physical objects equipped with various sensors related to certain aspects of their functionality. They enable to create rich digital models of anything physical or logical, from simple assets or products to complex cyber-physical environments. The collected sensor data is relayed to a processing system and applied to the DT. Once updated with such data, the DT can be used to run simulations, explore performance issues, and identify possible improvements – which can then be applied back to the original physical twin using bi-directional IoT connections.

Furthermore, Ditto acts as middleware, providing an abstraction layer for IoT solutions interacting with physical devices via the DT pattern. It can be seen as a toolkit, providing some core functionality (e.g., meta-model, database, different messaging protocols and connectors, REST APIs, etc.), while some other features must be written by users on top of them (e.g., domain-specific DT models, graphical user interfaces, device-side monitoring agents, etc.). Being part of a larger open-source ecosystem, it can be relatively easily integrated with some other technologies from the Eclipse stack, including various communication protocols, pub-sub messaging, and load balancing.

The default Ditto functionality was extended in the following ways:

- **GUI**, developed using the NodeJS/React stack, offers the required application-specific TA management features. Some illustrative screenshots are depicted in Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5.
- **Device-side monitoring agents** collect contextual information and receive updates.
- **Back-end service** exchanges and synchronizes desired and reported properties (i.e., collected by monitoring agents).
- **Extended DT definitions** of edge gateways including the cyber-physical-social context information (i.e., **Properties**) received from monitoring agents, as part of the application-specific fleet model.
- **Software assignment logic**, based on Resource Query Language (RQL)⁴ making use of the enriched DT definitions.

Device ID	Actions
+ no.sintef.sct.giot:mockupdevice	[edit] [delete]
+ no.sintef.sct.giot:raspberrypi_1	[edit] [delete]
+ no.sintef.sct.giot:raspberrypi_1_ssh	[edit] [delete]
+ no.sintef.sct.giot:tellu_axis_cam1	[edit] [delete]
+ no.sintef.sct.giot:tellu_gw1	[edit] [delete]

Figure 3. DTA GUI: list of managed devices.

³ <https://www.eclipse.org/ditto>

⁴ <https://github.com/persvr/rql>

Figure 4. DTA GUI: list of available TAs.

Figure 5. DTA GUI: selected a target device for TA deployment.

4.2.2 Deployment Language: an extension to Eclipse Ditto meta-model

Figure 6. Digital Twin meta-model capturing the multi-dimensional device context (an extension to Eclipse Ditto).

Ditto offers developers a meta-model, which in its simplest form enables modelling physical entities, referring to them as 'Things', using a JSON schema with the following key concepts (as depicted in Figure 6 and Figure 8):

- **Thing** is the top-level modelling concept for describing physical assets.
- **Definition** is included in every **Thing** (and optionally in **Features**) and essentially represents a URI linking to an external Web of Things (WoT) model. It describes how a **Thing** is structured and which behaviour/capabilities can be expected in an interoperable and standard manner.
- **Policy** enables to configure fine-grained access control. A specific policy defines who and how can access a specific resource.
- **Metadata** is Ditto's internal field to store technical information, e.g. version or creation/modification timestamps.
- **Attributes** are used to model rather static properties of a **Thing**, i.e. values that do not change as frequently as **Features**. They can be of any type and can be used to search for **Things**.
- **Features** are the central modelling concept to capture all run-time data and functionality of a **Thing** in a given application system. Users are allowed to define their own **Features** or extend existing WoT definitions. This is a key enabler for modelling the multi-dimensional context through more fine-grained **Properties**.
- **Properties** are used within **Features** to model individual run-time indicators of a **Thing**, e.g. to manage the status, the configuration or any fault information. Each **Property** can be either a simple scalar value or a complex JSON object. By using **Properties**, it is possible to implement the prominent **desired-reported** pattern widely adopted in DTs, wherein sensor measurements are reported upstream, while desired configuration updates are pushed downstream, until eventually **Properties** and **DesiredProperties** are in sync. As explained, this is the main mechanism for monitoring the state of the deployed TAs and managing the deployment.

A simplified example of a digital twin definition (i.e., and RPM gateway in the context of Pilot 2) used by the DTA component is depicted in Figure 7. The twin includes all main elements, including the multi-dimensional features. Please note the **reported_properties** field, which is used for twin synchronisation, as explained in more detail in the next subsection.

```

1  "thingId": "no.sintef.sct.giot:rpm_gateway_01",
2  "policyId": "no.sintef.sct.giot:rpm_policy",
3  "definition": "no.sintef.sct.giot:rpm_gateway:1.0.0",
4  "attributes": {
5    "manufacturer": "RPM Inc.",
6    "cpu_model": "Broadcom BCM2711"
7    "cpu_arch": "arm_v8",
8    "os": {
9      "name": "Raspberry Pi OS 11 (Bullseye)",
10     "kernel_version": "5.15.84"
11   }
12 },
13 "features": {
14   "cyber": {
15     "properties": {
16       "trust_agent": {
17         "enabled": true,
18         "version": "1.0.0"
19       },
20       "docker_engine": {
21         "enabled": true,
22         "version": "containerd.io_1.2.0-1_arm64.deb"
23       }
24     },
25     "reported_properties": {
26       "trust_agent": {
27         "enabled": false,
28         "version": "1.0.0"
29       }
30     }
31   },
32   "physical": {
33     "properties": {
34       "deployment_site": "hospital",
35       "gps_location": {
36         "latitude": "59.945283167835846",
37         "longitude": "10.713121330182533"
38       }
39     }
40   },
41   "social": {
42     "properties": {
43       "user_subscription": {
44         "type": "premium",
45         "expires": "2023-12-31T23:59:59Z"
46       }
47     }
48   }
49 }

```

Figure 7. A simplified digital twin of an RPM gateway with desired and reported properties.

4.2.3 Device state synchronisation through the ‘Desired-Reported Property’ pattern

The deployment function is implemented as two main components: the Fleet Manager and the Device Deployer. The central entity, Fleet Manager, determines which TAs should be deployed on each device. Concurrently, the Device Deployer oversees the actual deployment of the TAs on the devices. This clear division ensures efficient and organised deployment operations.

Communication between the Fleet Manager and Device Deployer is facilitated using the ‘Desired-Reported Property’ pattern (Figure 8). The Device Deployer consistently sends updates to the Fleet Manager regarding the status of each device, including the deployment and operational state of the TAs, every 30 seconds. If a change is deemed necessary by the Fleet Manager, ‘Desired Properties’ are created and sent to the Device Deployer, along with the previous Reported Properties. For example, in the example in Figure 7, the Fleet Manager updates the digital twin with the desired state of the trust agent to be ‘enabled’. The physical device, on the other hand, reports that the trust agent is still ‘disabled’ – this conflict in Desired and Reported Properties will trigger the deployment process until the two properties are eventually in sync.

More specifically, the deployment process on the individual devices starts with a three-way comparison by the Device Deployer between the Reported Properties, the Desired Properties, and the status of the devices. This comparison determines the necessary actions to be taken. For example, the absence of a TA in the Reported Properties, coupled with its presence in the Desired Properties, triggers the Device Deployer to initiate the deployment process. Same action will be triggered if the Desired Properties include a different version of TA than the reported one. Similarly, if

the reported properties include a deployed TA, but not started, whilst the desired properties include a running trust agent, the deployer will trigger the action to launch the TA. The Device Deployer uses the information in the Desired Properties, such as download links and package signatures, to carry out the deployment.

Throughout the deployment, the Device Deployer continues to send status updates to the Fleet Manager, ensuring real-time monitoring of the deployment progress. Upon completion, the alignment of the Reported Properties with the Desired Properties on the Fleet Manager's end signals the successful and efficient completion of the TA deployment or un-deployment.

Figure 8. Digital twin model with the 'Desired-Reported Property' pattern.

4.2.4 Device-specific adapters for tailored TA deployment

We now discuss the actual installation of TAs onto the devices. The design emphasises generality and extensibility, ensuring compatibility with diverse device types and allowing effortless introduction of new device categories. Currently, the system supports three different types of devices (plus one used for simulation and testing), each with unique TA compositions.

- **Docker:** This type involves any device equipped with a Docker engine, hosting a TA as a Docker container.
- **Linux SSH:** This category encompasses devices operating on a Linux operating system with open SSH access, wherein the TA operates as a shell script.
- **Device-specific HTTP API (Axis Camera):** Specifically for Axis cameras, the TA runs as an app within the camera, utilising the camera's REST API for deployment and lifecycle management.

In addition to these three adapters, a **simulation adapter** has also been developed for testing purposes. This virtual adapter mimics a physical device using a simple filesystem folder, with the simulated TA represented as a file within this folder.

Figure 9. Device-specific adapters for TA deployment.

An adapter oversees the device, handling connection, status checking, basic device info collection related to TA deployment, and the actual deployment of TAs. Each device is paired with a single adapter, which is capable of operating on the device itself (provided the device has an independent Internet connection) or externally on another computational unit with a secure connection to the target device. All the adapters inherit from the main abstract Adapter class that defines the basic methods (such as pinging the device, deploying software components, launching the components, etc.), as well as some common utility functions. All the adapters, once active, will regularly ping the devices and report the status to the DTA (more specifically – to its DT-based fleet manager), and at the same time, subscribes for any possible downstream commands. Whenever there is a TA update that requires actions on one of the devices, the adapter will launch the action on the corresponding device through the device-specific APIs and then report the status back to the DTA.

The system architecture employs a hierarchical structure to enhance adapter extensibility, as illustrated in Figure 9 above. An **AbstractAdapter** is designed to implement generic behaviours for all device types. This abstraction further breaks down into a set of operations, ensuring a robust and flexible framework for managing diverse device types and their corresponding TAs. This structure not only streamlines the deployment process but also fosters scalability and ease of integration for future device types and functionalities. A set of subclasses implement the device specific behaviours on these operations, such as ping the device status and deploy a TA. The **AdapterFactory** acts as a supervisor which receives the device twins from the fleet manager and determines which adapters in the machine should receive the twin model. If no adapter in the current machine matches the broadcasted device twin, the **AdapterFactory** will create it based on the information in the twin.

We use the adapter for Docker as an example. For devices that support a Docker environment, a TA operates as a Docker container. The essential requirement is for the device to enable the Docker Engine, which provides a REST API for communication.

This adapter operates both on the device itself or externally. It utilises the REST API to remotely communicate with the Docker engine on the device. The device twin, a digital replica of the device attributes and configurations, holds fundamental information such as the device’s IP and the Docker Engine API port. This information allows the adapter to call the **info** method of the Docker Engine to retrieve additional metadata about the device, including CPU architecture, OS distribution, and Docker version. This method also serves as a **ping** operation, ensuring the device is connected.

For deploying a TA, the adapter performs several sequential steps. It begins by downloading the Docker image for the TA using the URL provided in the device twin. Following this, it invokes the **loadImage** method of the Docker Engine to upload the image package into the device. To initiate the TA, the adapter calls **runContainer**, launching a

Docker container from the loaded image. Given that loading an image and initialising a container may be time-consuming, the adapter maintains continuous communication with the Docker Engine.

After sending the REST request, the adapter persistently checks the Docker Engine's information, including deployed images and container statuses, through a heartbeat mechanism. This real-time data is relayed to the fleet manager, keeping it abreast with the progress of the operations. This systematic and methodical approach ensures that the fleet manager continuously monitors the deployment process, ensuring the TA's smooth and efficient operation on Docker-supporting devices.

4.2.5 Downstream/Upstream communication between the DT platform and managed devices

In the context of communication between device adapters and fleet managers, a seamless and bidirectional flow is established using a MQTT server. This server houses dedicated topics for both downstream and upstream communication, ensuring a real-time and efficient exchange of information.

- **Upstream Communication:** In the upstream communication path, the fleet manager, or the DT platform, subscribes to a specific topic. All device adapters publish the real-time status of devices into this topic on a regular basis, currently set at every 30 seconds. The fleet manager, upon receiving these updates, locates the corresponding device twin in its database. It then proceeds to update the twin based on the received status, ensuring the device twin always reflects the most recent state of the device.
- **Downstream Communication:** Downstream communication follows a similar structured path. All device adapters subscribe to a separate dedicated topic on the MQTT server. The fleet manager publishes new twin models into this topic whenever a change occurs in the device twin. These changes are typically triggered by users editing the twin information, signalling the device adapters to update their operational parameters accordingly.

This structured communication framework, utilising the MQTT server and dedicated topics, ensures that both the fleet manager and the device adapters are constantly synchronised. The fleet manager stays updated with the real-time status of all devices, while the device adapters receive timely updates for any changes in the device twin models. At the same time, with the pub/sub communication, no static connections need to be maintained between the fleet manager and the device adapters, ensuring the flexibility of the system.

4.2.6 Verifying the trustworthiness of deployed TAs

The objective here is to ensure that the TA package set for deployment remains integral and unaltered from its original version as created by the trusted developer. This crucial verification process is two-fold, encompassing signature and verification, utilising the open-source signature tool, **Sigstore Cosign**.⁵ Notably, the online service typically used for storing public keys in **Cosign** is substituted with a dedicated DLT service within ERATOSTHENES.

- **Signature Process:** Post-development, as the TA is consolidated into a single package (such as a docker image), the developer signs this package using their private key. This signature, published alongside the package, serves as a marker of authenticity and integrity.
- **Verification Process:** Prior to any deployment by the device agent, the package undergoes a stringent verification process. The adapter collects the developer information for the TA from the device twin received from the fleet manager. Utilising this information, it queries the DLT to retrieve the developer's public key. Simultaneously, the adapter downloads both the package and its corresponding signature from the repository. With all elements in place, the adapter verifies the package against the signature using the developer's public key. A successful verification is the green light for the adapter to proceed with the actual deployment of the package to the device.

Within the DLT, a comprehensive list of trusted developers is maintained, complete with basic information and the public keys used for signing their TA packages. This meticulous approach to verification ensures that only authenticated and unmodified TA packages are deployed, upholding the integrity and security of the entire system.

⁵ <https://github.com/sigstore/cosign>

The architecture, thus, guarantees not only efficient and seamless deployment but also robust security and trust in the deployed TAs across all device types.

Please note that while the described one-off verification procedure is sufficient for the deployment of TAs, it is also important to continuously check whether the originally trusted TA still acts as expected (i.e. run-time attestation). This will be explored and reported in Task 2.5 'Automated recovery process of trust agents', where a run-time attestation failure will be used as one of the possible triggers for the TA recovery.

4.3 TA Deployment Process in the Context of Pilot 2

We now proceed with explaining how the proposed context modelling principles can be put in practice for TA deployment. For the reader's convenience, we will base our explanation on a relevant example from the project's Pilot 2 on smart healthcare.

4.3.1 Running Example from Pilot 2: Edge Gateways for Remote Patient Monitoring

The use case scenario refers to Pilot 2, where TELLU acts as a telemedicine provider offering Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM) services. From a DevOps engineer's perspective, a Docker-ised TA which needs to be deployed on RPM gateways and will be further used within the ERATOSTHENES ecosystem for trust calculations is similar to any other Docker-ised software component containing usual business logic. Therefore, we briefly explain the DevOps practices established at TELLU.

For each customer (typically – elderly people living at their own residences), they provide a healthcare gateway, i.e., a small single-board computer like Raspberry Pi, along with a set of medical sensors, cameras, and wearable emergency beepers. Each gateway collects measurements from Bluetooth-connected downstream sensors (e.g., blood pressure, glucose, and oxygen levels) or cameras (e.g., video stream for fall detection) and, before sending them to the back-end cloud service, may also perform some local (pre-)processing and aggregation. The patients and their caretakers have access to the data via a Web interface and a mobile app.

Some patients also opt for battery-powered portable gateways to have a possibility to carry them with the essential sensors whenever they are away, e.g., relocating to a summer house, travelling in a camper trailer or on a cruise ship. During these periods, the gateway connectivity switches from the residential WiFi network to a mobile one (3G or 4G). The gateways also differ in terms of their hardware capacity – i.e., the older versions are less powerful than the modern ones in terms of CPU, RAM, and available disk storage. At present, the device fleet comprises more than 500 gateways installed on the customers' premises, and there also exist several versions of the edge RPM software. More specifically, there is a version dependent on additional disk storage to accumulate sensor measurements and occasionally send them in batches, whenever a device is not connected to a WiFi network (e.g., in a trailer camper). Another version requires increased CPU and RAM resources, since it not just transfers data, but also implements local data pre-processing. There is also a version enhanced with support for image processing for fall detection, and therefore requires several cameras to be installed and connected. Depending on the subscription level, some versions provide only basic limited features, while some others are richer in terms of offered functionality. All these examples demonstrate how the heterogeneous context determines what RPM software version must be assigned and installed on each individual gateway in the fleet. The development team continuously updates the edge software by adding new features and patching bugs, following agile practices. After each DevOps cycle, typically executed on a weekly basis, there is a mass re-deployment involving many or sometimes all the devices in the fleet. To perform the assignment, it is required to parameterise each deployment and match them to devices and their cyber-physical-social context properties.

4.3.2 Demonstrations

The following two screen recordings demonstrate the current version of the DTA:

- **TA deployment on the Axis camera:** <https://youtu.be/OMdWhuhZSPw> The video shows how we use the tool to deploy software components (aka Apps for Axis cameras) into Axis cameras (used by TELLU in the context of the project's Pilot 2). We started with the fleet management GUI with 5 DTs of managed devices. We can zoom in to the camera's DT and see the device status is online. We can then assign a suitable TA to the camera. In the component, we provide the URL to the artifact (in Azure blob storage) and the name of its developer. After the assignment, the DT will be updated, which triggers the action of the adapter to

download the artifact, verify, load it into the camera, and finally try to start it. The last step is designed to fail due to the lack of device configuration, and therefore, the final status of the DT is 'stopped', which means successfully loaded, but not yet started.

- **Delayed TA deployment on the RPM gateway:** <https://youtu.be/t6Gyy5p4jfA> The second video shows how we deploy a TA (as a Docker container) on a TELLU gateway and demonstrate the important feature of delayed deployment. We start showing the status of the DT of the gateway, and it is shown as connected. After that, we disconnect it by unplugging the gateway from power. The status is reflected in the DT later. After that, we still try to assign the TA to the gateway, simulating a situation when the automatic assignment happens on all devices, but they cannot all be online at the same time. The assignment triggers action on the adapter, which downloads the artifact, verifies it, but cannot load it into the offline gateway. The status of the DT will be reported as 'unloaded'. After that, we plug the gateway back. At the same time, the DTA keeps attempting to deploy the component, and when the gateway is finally back online and functioning, the deployment eventually succeeds, and the status of the DT is updated to 'running'. From the developer's point of view, the assignment only happened once, even for the offline device, and once the device is online, the deployment is invoked automatically, as if the fleet deployment is delayed until the device is online.

5 Research and Scientific Innovation

The contents of this section summarise the scientific novelty underpinning the design and implementation of the described DTA component. The contents of this section overlap with the scientific paper “Context-Aware Digital Twins to Support Software Management at the Edge” accepted and presented at the 17th International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS 2023) in May 2023 [1]. The conference is ranked as Core-B conference, and the contributions of the paper received positive comments and feedback from the scientific community, especially due to the high relevance to industry and end users.

5.1 State of the Art

5.1.1 Digital Twins for Edge Fleet Management and Context Modelling

Among many research efforts on DTs applied to the IoT an important part belongs to research on DT interoperability and standards [2, 3]. An industry-driven effort in this context was done by Microsoft's Digital Twin Definition Language (DTDL)⁶ to provide more semantics to modelled physical environments. Albeit open source, it can primarily be used only within the Azure ecosystem. A similar attempt was made by the now-retired Eclipse Vorto.⁷ W3C Web of Things (WoT) has come up with another effort to standardise the modelling domain of IoT systems its Things Description model [3] – a formal information model and a common representation to describe the metadata and interfaces of IoT devices. In parallel, there is also an on-going effort to integrate the Semantic Web ontologies to provide more formal semantics and reasoning to the WoT.

Another relevant research field is **context modelling**, which has already been active for a few decades [4, 5]. Context modelling produces a formal or semi-formal description of the context information to create a context-aware system. Some recent attempts [6, 7] have started considering the cyber-physical dimension of the IoT and edge environments. There is a demand for context-awareness to assess trustworthiness of devices [8], as well as to complement application-specific analytics with enriched context information, e.g., disease diagnostics based on extra information from IoT sensors [9].

In summary, engineering of context-aware DTs is currently mostly *ad-hoc*, which is a challenge for quality-controlled development, deployment, and operation. Most works focus on a limited set of conventional metrics, not sufficient and suitable for edge software maintenance scenarios. A common limitation of the existing approaches is the hard-coded focus only on modelling the cyber-aspects of the managed physical entities, while more extensive modelling and coding is left to system administrators to be done manually.

5.1.2 Software Assignment

Assignment is an important part of all software management activities, be it the initial release or the follow-up maintenance. Unlike the centralised cloud model, where computing resources are relatively homogeneous, a fleet of edge gateways consists of distributed and heterogeneous devices, which have diverse multi-dimensional contexts in terms of hardware capacity, network connection, physical deployment, user preferences, etc.

Developers often need to maintain several software variants to fit such different device contexts. For example, some devices may require a variant tailored to a specific hardware capacity, while some others with limited connectivity may need a variant with lower bandwidth requirements. This can be formulated as a generic assignment problem – i.e., how to assign m software variants to n devices, so that each device is assigned with a variant that matches its context. At the same time, the whole fleet may also need to meet its global goals, e.g., maximise software diversity in the fleet for security purposes [10] or pick a sub-set of devices for preview and testing.

The existing tag-based fleet assignment mechanisms offered by device management platforms are sufficient for rather simple scenarios with a few device properties to consider. Devices can be logically grouped so that a particular maintenance update is applied only to a specific group. For example, grouping can be based on physical location or hardware architecture. However, this is not expressive enough to address software assignment scenarios with hundreds and thousands of devices, each having its own continuously changing multi-dimensional context – on the one hand, and multiple software versions – on the other.

⁶ <https://learn.microsoft.com/azure/digital-twins/concepts-models>

⁷ <https://www.eclipse.org/vorto/>

In these circumstances, correctly assigning software components in a precise and scalable manner heavily depends on up-to-date contextual information about managed devices, which seems to be not immediately available in existing solutions, which rely on general-purpose monitoring agents collecting a limited number of hard-coded performance metrics. In the absence of richer context-aware information about the managed fleet, using the default available tag-based assignment mechanisms is still possible, but would result in a complex collection of chained fine-grained *if-then* conditions – an error-prone and difficult-to-maintain solution.

The existing works on software assignment at the edge primarily focus on resource usage optimisation [11, 12, 13, 14], in which the objective function is typically based on generic infrastructure-level metrics, such as network latency [15], hardware resources utilisation, energy consumption, etc. and less frequent metrics, such as CO₂ footprint, monetary costs, number of tenants, etc. Optimisation metrics and related challenges are extensively surveyed in [16]. In all these works, edge software is typically treated as a black box, owned or managed by some external third party. As opposed to this, this proposed work tackles the software assignment problem from the perspective of an application provider, who owns and manages the whole vertical application system, including edge and cloud components. This means that software placement is mainly driven by application- and business-level requirements and evaluated against continuously monitored device-specific contexts, not strictly limited to the infrastructure level.

In this light, implementing software assignment requires modelling the application domain (i.e., software requirements and device context) and corresponding multi-dimensional constraints. Research approaches to solving complex constraints have resulted in several theories and tools, such as Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) [17], which offered several fully automated fleet assignment solutions based on various constraints and conditions. The SMT-based approaches are specifically popular and efficient due to their expressive and rich modelling language [18, 19, 20]. A common barrier for using SMT in practice is the gap between the abstract SMT models and the concrete representations, which required applying additional model-based techniques as a way of abstracting platform-specific details and providing an input for constraint solving. Nevertheless, they still require manually modelling the target system with some contextual information and testing the constraints.

Managing software updates across a large fleet of devices is an everyday task for the leading mobile OS providers, such as Apple and Google. At present, their adopted over-the-air update mechanism implements a publish-subscribe model, where mobile devices first get notified of and then fetch available updates through the centralised marketplace. Since smartphone fleets are rather homogeneous in terms of hardware and OSs, there is no challenge of multi-criteria software assignment as such, and the compatibility check is performed only once, upon the initial installation. Furthermore, in a fleet of smartphones there are typically no global system goals, such as even distribution of components or A/B testing.

5.2 Going Beyond the State of the Art

Summing up the relevant state of the art, existing approaches lack the support for context-aware software assignment at the edge. The developed DTA component partially tackles this challenge. Its implementation is driven by the two novel design principles, as described below.

5.2.1 Device fleet as the main level of abstraction

This design principle represents one step up from the conventional approach to maintain DTs of individual devices. By lifting the abstraction level, we are thus able to maintain a live view not only on the managed individual devices, but also on the dynamic inter-relations between them – something that can potentially play an important role when deciding what software management commands need to be applied to specific devices.

This is especially important when considering some global software management policies within a fleet, where assigning a software version to one device will depend on what version has already been assigned to another. For example, in DevOps, A/B testing is often implemented to test newly added features on a limited sub-set of staging devices before pushing them to production. Another example is the artificial **software diversity** – i.e., a common technique to improve system resilience, robustness, and security by deploying functionally-equivalent, yet different software versions on multiple systems [21]. In all such cases, updated software versions are required to be deployed only on a sub-set of the device fleet. Another common scenario is to limit the simultaneous use of some licensed software to a specific number of devices. Assignment in such circumstances will depend on whether other devices belonging to the same user are already running this software or not.

5.2.2 Multi-dimensional context awareness

Figure 10. Multi-dimensional context of a managed edge fleet.

In the context of rather static and homogeneous computing nodes (e.g., a computing cluster or a data centre), software management typically takes into consideration only the cyber-dimension of the target nodes, such as available hardware, networking configuration, OS version, already installed software, etc. As opposed to this, correctly assigning software components at the edge often needs to consider a much richer and more diverse context of edge infrastructures [22], i.e., going beyond just the traditional cyber dimension.

To this end, we propose adopting a three-fold context model, consisting of the **cyber**, **physical**, and **social** dimensions, as illustrated by Figure 10 and explained below:

- **Cyber dimension** covers the hardware and software aspects of edge gateways. For example, software assignment on a specific gateway may depend on connected sensors/actuators, OS version, security patches, networking interfaces (e.g., wireless/wired), power source (e.g., battery/constant power supply).
- **Physical dimension** primarily refers to where exactly an edge gateway is deployed physically. In ERATOSTHENES, and particularly in the Pilot 2, we focus on connected edge infrastructures deployed on end users' premises. For many scenarios (e.g., urban mobility, precision agriculture or environmental monitoring), this means that edge gateways may be exposed to changing and possibly harsh weather conditions, such as high/low temperatures or extreme humidity. Accordingly, vendors may opt for not assigning compute intensive AI-driven applications to those nodes already exposed to high temperatures not to cause overheating. Another example comes from telemedicine, where monitored patients are advised to take gateways with them even when travelling (e.g., in a camping trailer or in a cruise). In such cases, the updated physical placement or even the GPS location may be considered to assign a matching software update. The last but not the least, the physical placement is crucial for software assignment as far as security-related software management is concerned due to the direct effect on the current trustworthiness of the target device.
- **Social dimension** captures the human-related aspects of edge gateways, which, as previously explained, are deployed on end users' premises, and may be even equipped with some physical user interfaces for direct interaction. A good example of the social dimension is the subscription level, which defines the 'richness' of applications features a user might have. Coming back to the telemedicine example, only premium subscribers may be given a possibility to take their gateways on a trip, whereas non-premium subscribers will be blocked based on the updated GPS position. Another example from telemedicine is advanced AI-driven image recognition to be deployed directly on cameras for immediate fall detection or some other urgency.

Taken together, the three dimensions provide a useful conceptual framework for modelling heterogeneous device contexts. It is worth noting that these two design principles can be applied together to allow modelling situations where one device is part of a context of another device within a fleet. This way, we can capture the contextual inter-dependencies existing between the devices at the fleet level. For example, assigning a new software version to a device may depend on what other devices are connected and what software they are already running. Also, this could be

useful to model 'leaf' IoT devices which are not directly connected to the Internet, but via a gateway. This way, they may be logically represented as part of the gateway they are connected to.

6 Conclusions

The DTA component implemented in the context of Task 2.3 ensures that the required TAs are securely deployed and put into operation on target devices within the ERATOSTHENES ecosystem. Driven by the project pilots, the design and implementation of the tool follow the principles of extensibility, modularity, and decoupled communication. This deliverable not only describes the design and implementation details of the tool, but also positions it in the overall ERATOSTHENES ecosystem, highlights its relevance for the project's pilots, and demonstrates it in action using the project's Pilot 2 on connected RPM gateways.

As this is the first deliverable for Task 2.3, it still presents a work-in-progress implementation of the DTA component. This proof-of-concept acts as a base for the initial integrations with the pilot cases defined for ERATOSTHENES, as well as for the training in the context of Task 5.6 'Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings'. In the next iterations of the tool development in Task 2.3, a specific attention will be given to the robust technical implementation and usability making it usable by the project partners in the context of the relevant pilots. It is also expected that some valuable feedback and suggestions for further work, both in terms of functional and non-functional requirements, will be provided by the pilot providers during and after the training activities taking place in the context of Task 5.6.

It is also worth noting that with the kick-off of Task 2.5 'Recovery process of trust agents', further R&D in these two tasks will be closely related, as the deployment of TAs is seen as one of the default mitigation actions used for recovery. Thus, some further updates on the implemented DTA component will be included in the deliverables reporting on the work carried out in T2.5.

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